

1 Granulocyte specification from the HSC involves PRC1 function with CBX6 through PCGF5 and PRC2
2 function with CBX7 through Ezh1.

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7 A KH domain lncRNA, lncRNA-KHDRBS2 was transcribed together during HSC commitment to the
8 granulocyte lineage. The developmental function of polycomb involving the CBX gene family in the human
9 HSC was attributed in part or in whole to autosomal function of Xist and a somatic cell Xist RNP,
10 functioning together with PRC1 or PRC2. Polycomb interactions with Xist ncRNA are established and
11 involve, among other interactions, YY1 and Ezh2; these findings are novel and relate instead to the
12 recently described developmental functions of Xist in embryonic stem (hES) cell fate choice evidenced by
13 DANT transcript and silencing at the Dxz4 locus. Modest induction of KHNYN was also observed. Ilf2 and
14 Ilf3 were not appreciably activated. Ezh1 induction was accompanied by Ezh2 silencing. PCGF5 induction
15 was accompanied by modest repression of PCGF3 expression. We observed mobilization of Cbx
16 components resulting from Ezh2 shRNA depletion, providing independent genetic evidence for regulation
17 of the Cbx gene family by polycomb complex PRC2. Cbx epigenetic enzymes have specific,
18 non-interchangeable associations with both PRC1 and PRC2 polycomb complexes. Xist, the Xist RNP,
19 FIRRE and Xist RNP associated molecules like KHDRBS2/3 have important functions during normal
20 human development, both in the embryonic stem cell (found in humans in utero) and in the hematopoietic
21 stem cell (HSC).
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